

Preprint of the published version. Citation APA:

Sánchez-Olmos, C., & Viñuela, E. (2022). The end of the amateur music video dream (as we expected it): From YouTube to TikTok. En D. Hurwitz & P. Ordóñez Eslava (Eds.), *Music in the disruptive era* (pp. 3–22). Brepols.

The end of the amateur music video dream (as we expected it): from YouTube to TikTok

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Abstract

The Web 2.0 was presented in the early 2000s as the participative internet, a chance for users to take the floor, broadcast themselves and interact through blogs, wikis and social media. It was not only the access to, for instance, information and culture, but rather the affordance of consumers to create content, to become prosumers in an internet that appeared to be more democratic. This is the context for the creation of YouTube (2005), an online video platform that rapidly became the main medium for music consumption and that contributed to develop a rhetoric of unmediated and immediate success that rearticulated the romantic discourses particularly persistent in mainstream popular music, especially at a time when the TV talent-shows became ubiquitous in mass media. At the same time, YouTube became the arena for prosumers to implement remix practices and share user-generated content that resulted in numerous viral music phenomena, created and circulated outside of the music industry circuit: mash-ups, lipdubs, flashmobs, shred videos, music videos without music...

Since YouTube was created in 2005 many things have changed in its policy, becoming less democratic and more corporate in each modification. The aim of this chapter is to analyze how this corporatization contradicts the participatory rhetoric of online audiovisual media and imposes restrictions to the circulation of music by amateur prosumers. We establish three different periods in the evolution of music on the online audiovisual platforms, attending to technology advances, legal policies and musical practices: 1) the early years of YouTube (2005-2009), 2) the consolidation and commodification of musical videomemes in multi-channel networks (2009-2017) and 3) the development of new musical practices on social media and video apps like TikTok (2018-2021). We analyze paradigmatic examples in order to explore the dynamics that have characterized the circulation of music in each period. We

argue that official and amateur music videos are interdependent and have experienced a constant feedback that is central in the negotiations of music meaning. Thus, these interactions need to be studied to understand the way music circulates and is produced, consumed and prosumed in the digital era.

Introduction

YouTube has been one of the most important media for music video consumption since its birth in 2005. In its short history, YouTube has evolved from a democratic platform for sharing amateur videos to a transnational digital media corporation that makes profit from unpaid work. Nevertheless, it is one of the most representative sites of the way music circulates in the digital era, altering the traditional dynamics of production, distribution and consumption in a context of participatory culture. In this regard, prosumption has become a key practice for understanding an emerging hybrid model of music circulation where audiences occupy a central position and demand the right to participate. The aim of this chapter is to provide a historical snapshot of the evolution of musical practices on audiovisual digital platforms from YouTube to TikTok in terms of prosumption and practices performed by users.

Music is the most popular content on YouTube, but, as Liikkanen and Salovaara¹ have argued, it has not been studied yet in much detail, and there are musical practices and business strategies that need more attention, especially in the ecosystem of the web 2.0. One significant example is the cultural content created and uploaded by users to audiovisual platforms, considered as user-generated content (UGC), a concept related to the media convergence theorised by Jenkins² and Burges and Green³, among others. According to Ding *et al*⁴, one fifth of the uploaders contribute 72.5% of the videos uploaded to YouTube and one fifth of the most popular uploaders attract nearly the totality of the views. In fact, Van Dijck and Nieborg⁵ criticized the euphoric analysis about participatory culture on YouTube because most users, instead of creating, watch or download content created by others.

Beyond the numbers, UGC practices matter and affect music meanings. Moreover, Kim⁶ observed a transformation from user-generated content (UGC) into professionally-generated content (PGC), which shows the progressive institutionalization of YouTube. In this chapter we use the term UGC to refer to the music content uploaded by users; we are aware that many of these videos are professionally generated rather than amateur, but our aim is to focus on this professionalisation in order to explore to which extent YouTube is the dreamt place for amateur music video (that is a democratic, creative and high accessible site), and weather this platform has evolved as we expected.

We establish three different eras in the role of music on the online audiovisual platforms. The first one starts in 2005 with the creation of YouTube; we explain how this video streaming service rapidly became corporate and developed mechanisms to control copyrighted music.

¹ LIKKANEN – SALOVAARA 2015.

² JENKINS 2006.

³ BURGES – GREEN 2009.

⁴ DING *et al* 2011.

⁵ DIJCK – NIEBORG 2010.

⁶ KIM 2012.

The creation of VEVO in 2009 marks the beginning of a new stage; it entails a turn in the way music circulates and is managed on YouTube, and it sets the basis for the music business on the platform through the multi-channel networks. It is a time of successful YouTube amateur phenomena and videomemes that become rapidly monetized and commodified. Finally, the third period began in 2018 with the new agreements between record labels and social media (Facebook and Instagram), but it is definitely characterized by the rise of TikTok and the new musical practices developed in this video app.

I. The amateur music content: sharing in the YouTube community

The first stage in the evolution of music content on YouTube goes from its birth in 2005 until the foundation of VEVO in late 2009. Music videos and music content created by non-professional users were two of the most relevant formats of musical content in those years. For independent bands, YouTube marked a turning point in the evolution of music video at its early stage, helping to emancipate music videos from MTV. In other words, YouTube represented a hope for democratization for unknown musicians and underground music genres due to the difficulty in getting their music videos broadcasted on television in the MTV era, especially at a time of crisis in the music industry such as the 2000s⁷. There was hope for these artists, and we find paradigmatic successful examples such as the independent rock band OK Go and their music video «Here It Goes Again». The relevance of this case was that the band made a cheap, funny and amateur music video that won the Grammy Award in 2007 and also put this unknown band on the music charts in various countries. OK Go showed that musicians no longer depended on record labels or TV networks to disseminate their music. Through YouTube, music videos could exist independently from television channels. Consequently, independent record labels and musicians without a recording contract opened their own YouTube channels to promote their songs and to obtain direct profits via online advertisements inserted in their videos, such as banners, commercials and displays. Moreover, YouTube videos were easily spreadable through blogs and social media such as Facebook, which served to promote YouTube content especially in the early years of the platform. Therefore, in the era of YouTube music is not only valued as a form of artistic expression, but also, as data that attracts advertisements. In other words, as Negus pointed out, «music is a means to another end rather than an end in itself⁸».

The amateur music video broke the code of music videos as cultural texts; bedrooms, kitchens, etc. became settings for musical performances. In 2006, Lital Mizel uploaded «Hey» by Pixies, a homemade dance performance considered the first amateur and user-generated music video that became viral⁹. However, even if many of the practices developed on YouTube at this stage were quite democratic and followed the spirit of its claim, «Broadcast yourself», copyright infringement became an issue from the very beginning. Users uploaded both amateur and official content to their channels, and YouTube was accused of allowing this practice. Significantly, Viacom, former founder of MTV, filed a lawsuit against Google and YouTube in 2007 that provoked the implementation of the Video ID, a digital fingerprinting system to identify and manage copyrighted content. That year YouTube also launched the Partner Program, a system to share the revenue produced by advertising on the site with the author (usually 45% to YouTube and 55% to the video

⁷ EDMON 2014.

⁸ NEGUS 2019, p. 376.

⁹ HEARSUM – INGLIS, 2013.

uploader). Thus, two years after its creation the platform had the infrastructure to make profit from the content they were hosting, and the business was already working. Three years later, YouTube created a new copyright policy Content ID which included Video ID and Audio ID.

Copyright infringement is a consequence of the media convergence that forced major record labels to adapt to a new media ecology. From the economic perspective, YouTube challenges old media¹⁰, though it has harnessed its ability to host copyrighted materials into achieving market dominance progressively, making profit from it¹¹. Copyright infringement is still an issue nowadays, the controversial Article 13 of the «Directive on Copyright in the Digital Single Market» (2019) is vague, and it might affect the status of amateur and user-generated content. The European Union requires YouTube to take the responsibility for the copyrighted content uploaded by users to the platform, whereas the current Content ID gives copyright owners the right to claim ownership.

Nonetheless, the topic of YouTube's democratic spirit was deeply installed in the society, and the music industry took advantage of it. As Robert Strachan argues, «the idea of a democratized media has in itself become a central part of the discursive practices of contemporary marketing campaigns¹²». Thus, in those years several new artists appeared affirming that they started their music careers uploading videos to YouTube. It is the case of Justin Bieber, Ed Sheeran, Charlie Puth, Lana del Rey and Shawn Mendes, among others. It is difficult to say if this was true for all (or any) of them, and, if so, it is hard to value to which extent their early performances on YouTube played a significant part in their success. But, undoubtedly, this narrative served to authenticate¹³ their star persona and articulates the idea that anyone can make it in the music business, a rhetoric especially well accepted at a time when TV talent-shows are a big success. In other words, the music industry practically said, «broadcast yourself on YouTube and we will discover you».

Still, at this first stage of YouTube we may find many unpredicted phenomena; practices that had significant impact on the music business and that (apparently) were not planned by the industry. It is the case of the Rickrolling, a meme that consists in a bait and switch with a disguised hyperlink that redirects to the music video for Rick Astley's «Never Gonna Give You Up» (1987). This meme gained mainstream attention in 2008, when YouTube users uploaded thousands of videos registering rickrolling practices in all kinds of situations (TV programmes, schools, offices, sport events, etc.). As a result of that, Rick Ashley increased his popularity and relaunched his career. This was an unexpected phenomenon that responded to the massive acceptance of this prank on the internet, and it demonstrated the agency of YouTube users and their practices, but also the benefits of virality for the music industry. This was probably the first massive viral practice involving music on YouTube. Rickrolling continued during the next decade and it was even replicated in 2010 with a song known as «Trololo» by Russian singer Eduard Khil, although it had less impact. Moreover, Rickrolling became a growing meme trend among tiktokers in 2020, and it spread with the hashtag #ricktok.

II. From User-Generated Content to Professional-Generated Content

¹⁰ KIM, 2012.

¹¹ SÁNCHEZ-OLMOS – VIÑUELA 2021.

¹² STRACHAN 2017, p. 36.

¹³ MOORE 2001.

YouTube started with the idea of allowing amateur users to publish their videos «to share» with what the founders of YouTube called «the community». However, since YouTube was sold to Google in October 2006, it has gradually evolved into an institutional, corporate, and commercial platform where videos are not only entertainment but also an input to make money attracting advertisements¹⁴. In fact, this democratic idea of participatory culture contrasts with the economic revenues that music content generates on YouTube. This process developed parallel to the increase in the number of views; by 2010 YouTube was the third most visited website in the world¹⁵. This data impeded the creation of multi-channel networks to promote, manage and monetize the content of certain channels that boosted their number of views and subscriptions generating more revenues.

The era of multi-channels: VEVO

One example of multi-channel is VEVO, a video hosting service aimed at monetizing its artists' music videos. VEVO is owned by Google, Abu Dhabi Media, Sony Music and Universal Music. According to Social Blade¹⁶, VEVO is the most-viewed channel on YouTube, with over ten billion views. This multi-channel network exclusively hosts its own artists' channels. Other musicians can neither access VEVO nor benefit from the advantages it offers, such as audience traffic, which translates into advertising revenue, or the powerful promotional strategies of the network. Although YouTube has indeed represented a process of democratization for unknown musicians, the fact remains that the most-viewed channels still belong to multinational conglomerates. This professionalization of YouTube also affected musicians without a recording contract, that were (once again) left apart from the system.

However, VEVO was not satisfied with hosting the most viewed music videos and the channels of the most popular artists in mainstream music, the multi-channel implemented strategies to fuel the spreadability of the videos it was hosting. It is the case of the marketing campaign launched to promote the video of Andy Grammer's «Keep Your Head Up» in 2011. This was the announcement posted on the site of VEVO: «Choose from hundreds of potential scenes and outcomes to create the perfect video. Watch and share your favourite version with friends. Check back November 15th to see the most popular version of the video as chosen by our viewers!¹⁷». Music video contests became quite popular on YouTube at that time, and interactive videos were also an innovative tool to favour participatory culture and engagement. The most famous example is the interactive video of Arcade Fire's «We Used to Wait» (2010), that, according to Rebeca Kinsky, «tapped into a zeitgeist shifting distinctly from viewers as audience to viewers as users and co-authors of digital experience¹⁸». Undoubtedly, these kinds of videos enhanced the agency of the audience and encouraged them to interact with the content in many different ways: creating, sharing, liking, commenting... on their social media, generating traffic and contributing, in the end, to the viralization of a particular song and video.

Economic and cultural approaches to musical user-generated content

¹⁴ BURGESS – GREEN 2009; KIM 2012.

¹⁵ HEARSUM – INGLIS 2013, p. 485.

¹⁶ <https://socialblade.com/youtube/user/vevo>

¹⁷ <https://bit.ly/3qgIUOG>

¹⁸ KINSKY 2014, p. 8.

In this section we critically review from an economic and cultural perspective the democratic conception of YouTube by exploring new practices in music consumption and by analysing musical user-generated content, i.e. mashups, lipdubs, music videos without music, etc. From an economic perspective, it is worth noting that this content can be monetized due to its spreadable and memetic features, since they attract both viewers and advertisers to YouTube. Significantly, the *IFPI Digital Music Report 2014* confirmed that YouTube Content ID system is «allowing the streaming of non-official user-generated content such as mashups to be licensed and monetised, rather than removed for infringing copyright¹⁹». Consequently, user-generated content was generating more revenues than official videos already in 2013. In other words, the original spirit of YouTube, «broadcast yourself» changed into something like «broadcast me (so I can make profit from your creations)».

On the other hand, prosumers may gain credit and massive audiences on YouTube, as it happened with the phenomena we are analysing, although they do not get revenues from their creations unless they are hired by multi-channel networks. Often, these viral phenomena become a regular content of entertainment networks that produce them professionally and increase their popularity. In a previous work²⁰ we have demonstrated that these music phenomena get more likes and become more viral in social media than the original music videos, that is they generate traffic and engagement, and, in the end, they create a new space for music consumption that coexists and promotes the official music videos. In fact, this situation has affected even the aesthetics of mainstream music video, and many official videos began to incorporate scenes and elements that were capable of triggering parodies²¹. Thus, parodies of music videos like «Gangnam style» (2012) by Psy or «Wrecking Ball» (2013) by Miley Cyrus contributed to their popularity and generated income, and, in both cases, the aspects and situations parodied were recurrent.

These amateur phenomena have become integrated in the economic structure, and they have encultured new practices of music pro/con-sumption in digital audiences that interact and enrich the experience with the official videos. This is why non-official content is so important to explore how mainstream popular music circulates since the creation of YouTube. Prosumption is more than a ludic activity, it can be read as a conversation on music that participates in the negotiation of meanings and in which we can explore all sorts of cultural and political values and the articulation of identities. As John Richardson and Claudia Gorbman argue, «we don't fully understand film, television, games, music videos, video art (...) until we understand what people do with them²²». In other words, the cultural perspective matters to understand the value of musical user-generated content beyond its economic implications.

Prosumption happens in a web 2.0 ecosystem that allows new forms of communication; however, practices do not develop only according to the technical possibilities of media, but rather to a much more complex set of procedures that we adopt and normalize in our relationship with technology. Thus, we can talk of the development of a digital culture defined by how we use digital tools. Carol Vernallis argues that the way we use audiovisual technology changes our relationship with content. Nowadays, we are used to editing images and clips in our computers and phones; we cut, paste, resize, move and manipulate them in many different ways with tactile gestures that become habitual in the way we consume and

¹⁹ IFPI, p. 20.

²⁰ SÁNCHEZ-OLMOS – VIÑUELA 2017.

²¹ VERNALLIS 2013.

²² RICHARDSON – GORBMAN 2013, p. 32.

customize photos, films, video games, music videos²³... In this regard, consumers «redefine the affordances of these technologies and the ways in which they can interact with them to consume music²⁴».

This is why we can consider prosumption as a practice that characterizes music consumption in the digital era. We put the focus on the interactions with music content, paying attention to how prosumers listen to music being conscious of their capabilities to manipulate the official content and create memes. Nicholas Cook argues that new technologies facilitated «different ways of experiencing music and of creating music to experience²⁵». He coined the term «multimedia mentality» to enhance the position of consumers that listen to music aware of their agency and to describe the processes implied in the creation of meaning in the digital era, in which any text is always susceptible of being manipulated and re-signified.

Nicholas Cook highlights the role of audiovisual content on YouTube in these prosumer practices, and approaches mash-up as a central videomeme phenomenon in contemporary mainstream music. Thus, the creation of music memes has to be understood as a key practice in the way music circulates nowadays. Elsewhere, we have argued that memes, such as literal video versions, shreds and music videos without music, actively participate in «the negotiation of canons and the re-signification of songs and music genres²⁶». Thus, it is not only that memes contribute to viralize particular songs and music videos, but they are also capable of altering music meanings and of revising the aesthetics of a period and the genres and artists that are considered representative of an era.

Videomemes and YouTube phenomena began to gain popularity in the early 2010s. Though most of them delve their roots in the early years of the platform (even before YouTube was founded) and were created and uploaded by amateur users, it is in the multi-channel networks where most of these productions went viral. They normally act as boosters to viralize incipiently popular practices and videomemes on the internet. As Patrick Vonderau argues, «YouTube is always ready-to-hand, but more and more the end point of content discovery rather than its first window. Multi-channel networks have made the site's instrumentality as an infrastructure for organizing market practices visible²⁷». In previous works²⁸ we have demonstrated how, normally, the most-viewed videos of a videomeme category (i.e mash-up, literal video version, shred...) are hosted by professional entertainment channels signed by multi-channel networks. It is the case of music videos without music; considering the 22 most viewed up to 2016, 12 were uploaded to channels inserted in multi-channel networks (House of Halo and College Humour) and nearly all the videos were uploaded in 2014 and 2015; whereas 8 videos were created and uploaded by Mario Wienerroither, an independent youtuber credited as the initiator of this practice on YouTube, most of them between 2008 and 2009²⁹.

However, multi-channel networks are not the only agents that monetize user-generated content. We also find initiatives that promote and viralize particular YouTube phenomena and contribute to circulate and to increase the revenues of a song on the platform. An

²³ VERNALLIS 2013.

²⁴ NOWAK 2016, p. 29.

²⁵ COOK 2013, p. 55.

²⁶ SÁNCHEZ-OLMOS – VIÑUELA 2021, p. 220.

²⁷ VONDERAU 2016, p. 368.

²⁸ SÁNCHEZ-OLMOS – VIÑUELA 2017; 2021.

²⁹ SÁNCHEZ-OLMOS – VIÑUELA 2017, p. 3642.

example is the lipdub, a category of meme music video recorded in a single sequence shot in which participants lip-synch the song. The first examples of this practice dates from the early years of YouTube, but it went viral in 2009 and 2010. We can find lipdubs recorded in many different contexts, it actually became a popular practice for teambuilding in offices, but undoubtedly it was in high schools and colleges where this practice became popular, impulsed by projects like «University Lipdub³⁰» (2008).

In fact, the lipdub made by the students of the Faculty of Communication at UQAM (Université du Québec at Montreal) in September 2009 is considered the one that drove this practice viral internationally. This video had over ten million views by 2012, and its success was echoed by the press and televisions all over the world. The media impact also favoured the launching of multiple lipdub contests organized by youth TV programmes and brands like J&B and Citroën³¹. The song used in this lipdub was The Black Eyed Peas' «I Gotta Feeling», a single released on May 21st 2009³². The official music video was not uploaded to YouTube (hosted by VEVO) until December that year. Thus, the lipdub created by the UQAM students circulated three months before and, to a certain extent, it served as an unofficial music video. Moreover, this song happened to be especially adequate for lip dubs, and many other YouTube users selected it for their creations.

Of course, the song was very popular that Summer, and this certainly explains its use when the lipdub phenomenon went viral in 2009, but its formal features also facilitated the amateur production of a lipdub. First of all, the song is a mid-tempo with a solid 4-beat rhythmic pattern, which allows regular camera movements and facilitates the coordination of participants to articulate the lip-synching. The bassline repeats an ostinato that sustains a conventional harmonic structure (I-IV-VI-IV), and the transitions between sections are normally emphasized with collective expressions such as «hey» or «ho», facilitating audio-visual synchrony. The melody is syllabic, and it keeps the flow of the tempo all the time. Besides, the song alternates solo and choral parts, which is perfect to combine solo and choral scenes in the video. Finally, the lyrics are optimistic and encourage us to have fun and enjoy life. All this made the song popular in the lipdub phenomenon and, as a result of that, The Black Eyed Peas monetized the millions of views to all the videos via the YouTube Content ID. Considering that many students shared these videos in their social media, the song spread rapidly and the views on YouTube experienced an exponential growth. But, even more important, thousands of internet users engaged with the song (and ultimately with the band) by creating their own lipdub version, and made it the leitmotiv of a memorable moment. Thus, these new forms of experiencing music through prosumption normally imply the creation of durable affective connections to songs and artists that, in the long term, are very profitable for the music industry.

However, some might say the case of «I Gotta Feeling» is not a big deal, because it was already a hit when the lipdub boomed. More peculiar is the case of the Harlem Shake, another YouTube phenomenon that used a scarcely known song of the same name, published by dj. Baauer (Harry Rodrigues) on May 22nd 2012. On January 30th 2013, American youtuber Filthy Frank uploaded a video dancing to a fragment of the song with his friends. Three days later, Australian youtubers The Sunny Coast Skate uploaded to their channel another dance version that configured the formal features of the videomeme, and it began to spread. A few

³⁰ <http://universitylipdub.com/>

³¹ VÍÑUELA 2013, p. 180.

³² The music video was released on June 2nd 2009, though not on YouTube, but on Dipdive, a social network created by Will.i.am (member of The Black Eyed Peas).

days later, the influential culture site BuzzFeed echoed the meme, and youtuber Hiimrawrn, employee of the multi-channel network Maker Studios (bought by Disney in 2014), uploaded his version. According to Michael Soha and Zachary J. McDowell, «at its peak, the Harlem Shake meme was immensely popular and generative (with nearly 4,000 YouTube uploads per day). It only took about 40 days to reach 1 billion views on YouTube, half the time that it took for `Gangnam Style`³³».

Basically, the Harlem Shake is a 30 seconds video structured in two parts. In the first 15 seconds we see an individual dancing in a quotidian context while the rest of the participants do not pay any attention to him/her. When the bass drops the video cuts and all the participants appear dancing, normally in disguise. The last seconds of the video usually are in slow motion. The structure is not complicated and videos are short, which is important to facilitate both production and consumption of the meme. Again, the features of the song seem to guide the visuals and to play an important part in the success of this phenomenon. The first part of the piece is a 4-beat rhythmic pattern that emphasizes every pulse; at the same time, tension is increased by including progressive division levels in the drums. Besides, synthesizers play several ascendent melodic lines using a frequency sweep to generate a dense texture and a crescendo effect. Altogether configures a typical structure of electronic dance music when the dj. wants to build a climax. The release of this tension is in the second part of the piece, when the bass becomes prominent and sustains a smooth groove with an emphasis in the third pulse of the 4-beat bar, while the melodic layers remain mostly plain.

Between both sections there is a momentaneous silence that tenses the musical discourse and where we only hear a glitch sound. According to Robert Strachan, glitch sounds are a powerful resource normalized in electronic music and «employed towards a variety of affective and expressive ends³⁴». In the Harlem Shake, the glitch highlights the cut in the video, and it is the instant when the scenario changes and all the participants start dancing disguised. Carol Vernallis defines glitches in videomemes «as a surprise, such that the viewer wonders whether there´s a technical error³⁵», and she reads its use in the Harlem Shake as a time out, a temporal ellipsis that establishes a causal relation between the two sections of the video.

The A-B, tension-release structure and the cause-effect dynamic of the Harlem Shake seems fundamental in the success of this videomeme. Thousands of versions circulated on YouTube as prosumers got involved in a kind of challenge that was made explicit both in the title of the second version of the meme by Filthy Frank: «Do the Harlem Shake» (February 2nd), and in the head of the article published in BuzzFeed: «Have You Done A Harlem Shake Video Yet?» (February 7th). YouTube Content ID identified Baauer as the unique author of the song and he received all the revenues; no prosumer, not even the youtubers that created the videomeme, received any reward. But the song was created sampling two other songs: «Maldades» (2006) by Héctor «El Father» Delgado and «Miller Time» by Plastic Little, so Baauer had to «cut the deals with both³⁶».

Undoubtedly, the copyright law does not fit and it is not fair in a case like the Harlem Shake. We may wonder who is the author of this phenomenon, because Baauer´s piece was created sampling previous songs, it would have had a discrete success without the videomeme

³³ SOHA – MCDOWELL 2016, p. 1.

³⁴ STRACHAN 2017, p. 140.

³⁵ VERNALLIS 2013, p. 191.

³⁶ SOHA – MCDOWELL 2016, p. 6.

created by both youtubers Filthy Frank and The Sunny Coast Skate, and, at the same time, the meme wouldn't have gone viral without the echo of BuzzFeed and the version uploaded by the influencer Hiimrawrn. And, of course, none of these steps would have guaranteed the success of the phenomenon.

Prosumers are disruptive, they problematize copyright laws by participating in YouTube phenomena, this is why Nicholas Cook claims for a multimedia mentality where «meaning and originality is performative, emerging out of contexts of use and reuse³⁷». He recalls Toynbee's concept of «social authorship» that intends creativity as a process «manifested across series of texts rather than at the level of the individual artwork³⁸». This swift would entail not only a modification of the copyright laws, but also a radical change in the romantic conception of artwork as an autonomous and finished piece created by the inspiration and the genius of a single author. In other words, we should stop conceiving art as a product and start thinking of it as a practice. Interactivity, prosumption and the circulation of user-generated content opened the door to new relations with music, and, as we will see in the next section, this is a process that has been intensified in the last few years.

III: From uploading videos to TikToking

In December 2017 Facebook announced a deal with Universal Music that allowed users to upload licensed music to the social networking site (both for Facebook and Instagram). By March 2018 the three major record labels were in the deal. This move marks a turning point in the relation of these social media with music, which was understood as a key medium to achieve a dominant position in the trends of video sharing. The agreement avoided copyright claims to Facebook and facilitated the implementation of new tools for users to experience music and videos, encouraging them to add music to their memories and moments. Significantly, in June 2018 Instagram allowed to include music in the stories.

Until then, copyrighted music was shared in these social media embedding the link to a music or video stream service (Spotify, SoundCloud, YouTube, Vimeo...). Thus, these services gained traffic through this practice. Both music and video streaming services continue to be the main media for music consumption, but the possibilities offered by Facebook and Instagram since 2018 aimed at promoting practices that change our relationship with music and brought them closer to the functions offered by the video apps. This was nothing new at the time, Vine was the first video app; it was created in 2013 and it gained popularity when it was purchased by Twitter, though it closed in 2017. Thus, this was a great opportunity for Facebook and Instagram to hit that market, but TikTok appeared in the Summer of 2018 and came out on top.

Created in 2016 by ByteDance in Beijing, TikTok is the first Chinese digital platform that succeeded in Western countries. The company is the result of the merge between ByteDance and Musical.ly; the latter was already an enormously popular music app where lip-syncing was a consolidated entertainment practice. TikTok is currently the world's leading platform for short videos made by dilettantes, most of which create, edit and share content with popular music. Nowadays, this social media enjoys over 1 billion users, who are mainly

³⁷ COOK 2013, p. 71.

³⁸ Toynbee quoted in COOK 2013, p. 71.

teenagers. With this app, users create a profile for uploading short music videos, which are mostly lip-synched clips between 15 seconds and 1 minute long. This phenomenon shows a new way of consuming music with a high level of consumer engagement. Users listen to music in the knowledge that they can create their own videos with the songs and measure their popularity by sharing them on this social network. Moreover, TikTok has become a new medium for teenagers to discover music and to keep up to date with the latest trends. Little research has been conducted into the role of music on this app, which as of 2019 has become one of the most popular apps³⁹. Even if Instagram has imitated its functions launching the tool Reels in August 2020, it did not succeed to attract TikTok users. In contrast with YouTube, which has gradually become more professional and business-orientated over the last decade, most of the users in TikTok are (still) amateur.

The success of TikTok mirrors the consolidation of new practices in the social media ecosystem during the last few years. Probably, the most evident innovation is the ephemeral character of most of the content posted. The popularity of the Instagram stories, a tool launched in 2016 (copying the dynamics of Snapchat) was determinant to intensify the use of social media, especially among teenagers. The content uploaded to stories expires after 24 hours, which encourages users to post their life «instants» as they are happening. This implies a constant use of social media that becomes part of most users' everyday life. Continuous presence on the network is more important than the quality or the relevance of the content (normally photos or videos) because they won't be accessible on the users' profile after it expires. This dynamic of being up to date on social media passed on to the consumption of music also in other platforms. Significantly, in the last few years, we assisted to a constant and exponential record break in the most-viewed videos online in 24 hours: 3 times in 2018, 5 on 2019 and 8 on 2020, and nearly all of them are music videos hosted on YouTube.

Nonetheless, there's a more subtle milestone in the use of social media that affects the consumption of music. Nowadays, more users interact with music, prosumption has become common and participatory culture is more extended than ever, especially through video apps like TikTok. This is a turning point in the way we consider prosumption; in previous works⁴⁰ we have observed that in most of the YouTube phenomena (lipdubs, shreds, literal video versions...) a few prosumers, normally professional or skilled users, created a high percentage of the most viewed videos, and participatory culture consisted mainly in sharing, liking and commenting on the most popular productions⁴¹. Thus, the center of prosumption in these phenomena was the videomeme, i.a. the product that was created normally by manipulating previous official productions; whereas viral phenomena on TikTok do not rely that much on the success of particular videos, but on the massive participation of the users (i.a. in the practice) that circulate their contribution among the community using hashtags. Besides, these mainly amateur contributions consist on videos where users appear dancing to or lip-synching an official song, and they normally edit them using the tools of the video app., whereas in many YouTube phenomena the raw material (music and image) are official productions, and the videomeme is created using audiovisual editing software and then uploaded to the platform. Thus, TikTok facilitates immediate practices and amateur production.

³⁹ In 2019 TikTok was the third most-downloaded app worldwide. In 2020 it reached the top 1.

⁴⁰ SÁNCHEZ-OLMOS – VIÑUELA 2017; 2021.

⁴¹ Moreover, prosumers also created many compilations of videomemes gathering «the best», «the top» or «the funniest» examples in each category.

In the report «The Year on TikTok: Top 100» (2020) we observe an emphasis in the sense of community and in the creativity of the users, encouraging creative practices and active participation in the network. «Innovation» and «creation» are terms that commonly appear in the discourse of TikTok, a rhetoric that empowers users and celebrates their role in the TikTok community. The app offers the tools to edit the videos, but it also offers materials to work with, in particular songs that are used as the soundtrack for most of the videos, more often to dance or to lip-synch. According to Raphaël Nowak, «the technological component that partakes in contemporary modes of music consumption contributes to redefining individuals' approach to music and their music taste⁴²». And, to a certain extent, these practices recall Marshall McLuhan's motto «medium is the message».

However, in order to understand how TikTok users interact with music we shouldn't focus that much on what the app technology enables to do, but rather on what people really do with it. In other words, technology affords but does not determine the relation with music. Robert Stachan argues that «an expectation of where music will be listened to (and by whom) is key to understanding how social uses might engender specific creative decisions⁴³». Similarly, prosumption is never an autonomous act and prosumers always bear in mind the context in which their content will circulate, in this case the TikTok «community». Juan Bermúdez uses Chris Small's concept of «musicking» to study TikTok from an (ethno)musicologic perspective, conceiving this social network as a space for fieldwork to explore musical practices⁴⁴. In this regard, the videos should be understood as «mediating mechanisms via which cultural practices are originated, adopted and (sometimes) retained within social networks⁴⁵».

We will briefly approach the TikTok phenomenon of the dance challenges, undoubtedly the most popular musical content on TikTok. In fact, the most followed accounts on TikTok, Charli D'Amelio and Addison Rae, belong to dancers. Dance challenges are nothing new in social media; we can mention Harlem Shake (2013) and Floss Dance (2018) as two previous successful examples that went viral on different platforms. Moreover, dance crazes have always used audiovisual media to become popular; it is through films, television or music videos that we knew about the madison, the moonwalk, the vogue and the Macarena, among many others. However, TikTok is especially suitable for these phenomena. On the one hand, the video app allows recording the video and editing it with your phone, you don't need any other hardware or software. You can add filters (even presets like the «beauty mode»), different effects, add text and stickers, select transitions, apply slow/fast motion, reverse speed, etc. A whole range of options that are easy to use. These are tools that facilitate interaction and offer many possibilities in the synchronization of dance gestures with music. On the other hand, dance serves to show off and to demonstrate body skills, which are highly valued in social media. At the same time, «challenges also create user communities around creative amateur peer creation and participation in social online environments⁴⁶». They activate practices that spread through hashtags and any user can join. Besides, dance is a powerful resource to express yourself, to communicate, and of course to interact with music. Significantly, academies are already noticing that TikTok has increased the interest of teenagers in dance.

⁴² NOWAK 2016, p. 122.

⁴³ STRACHAN 2017, p. 127.

⁴⁴ BERMÚDEZ 2020.

⁴⁵ BURGESS 2008, p. 102.

⁴⁶ KLUG 2020, p. 7.

It is not easy to determine whether popular dance challenges emerge and spread organically from the altruist action of TikTok amateur users or if they rather respond to marketing strategies. Whatever the case may be, the music industry is aware of its benefits and there are moves that seem to be thoroughly designed to viralize dance challenges on this network, like posting a brief passage of a song on social media before the release of the single aiming to trigger prosumption among fans. Besides, popular tiktokers are paid from record labels to create content with their songs, it is the case of Epic Records paying Charli D'Amelio to post videos dancing to Michael Jackson songs and using the hashtag #EpicRecordsPartner.

It is worth noting that these TikTok practices do not involve the image of the artists, but their music. They are not the focus of a parody anymore like in videomemes, their image is absent in the videos and they remain «safe» in a secondary position, it is the prosumer that shows off. Consequently, the most popular accounts related to music belong to tiktokers, not to artists, as it happens on Instagram or Facebook. We argue that, since 2018, we are assisting to a swift in the dynamics of the amateur music video from content to practice and from artist to user. In this context, the industry is taking a more collaborative stand, inviting social media users to participate, encouraging them to «broadcast with them». Thus, users gain agency, though, at the end of the day, prosumption remains unpaid work and revenues are always for the copyright holders.

Conclusions

In this chapter we have drawn an overview of the role of music on YouTube and TikTok. We have approached these platforms as the main media for music consumption in the last decade and as determinant agents in the way we relate to music. In this century, the evolution of online communication has gone through different phases that affected the way we communicate; in this regard, we understand music as a powerful medium for self-expression that has a key role in the articulation of identities. In this context, our relation to music has constantly changed, which allowed us to establish three different stages in the musical practices we have developed on the online audiovisual platforms. We argue that the dichotomy between «digital natives» and «digital immigrants»⁴⁷ is not useful anymore to explain the dynamics of different generations in the use of the internet. There is an inclination to approach the digital era as a monolithic period, but we have demonstrated that there are practices that were central in a certain period that are already obsolete, while others emerge affecting the ways we use technology and interact with cultural contents, such as music.

We have approached both official and amateur musical content on YouTube and TikTok; even if they have different origins and procedures, we wanted to show how they are closely interrelated. It is not only that they share space on audiovisual platforms and social media, but we have also demonstrated their constant feedback and the numerous ways in which one depends on the other. Thus, we have explored how many YouTube musical phenomena had their origins in the context of user-generated content but achieved massive audiences and became viral when multi-channel networks promoted and produced them professionally, like in the case of the Harlem Shake or the music videos without music. Besides, official music videos and musical user-generated content facilitate the circulation of music on the internet, and they both participate in the negotiations of meaning.

⁴⁷ PRENSKY 2001.

YouTube was completely corporate only a couple of years after its creation. We have observed how the management of copyrighted music was a big issue from the very beginning, and how the platform implemented an infrastructure to monetize and commodify amateur practices. However, our position is not apocalyptic (in Eco's terms); even if most of the revenues are managed by multi-channel networks, prosumers are constantly developing new practices that challenge the stability of the business, and audience behaviour is difficult to predict and it changes rapidly. We argue that YouTube and social media are uneasy fields and a perfect terrain for disruptive practices related to music and other cultural productions. Thus, when a viral phenomenon is commodified there are already others gaining popularity. This has been a never-ending process since the creation of YouTube in 2005, and it was intensified on social media in recent years.

We have paid special attention to the transformations in the role of music on social media since 2018. We focused our attention especially on TikTok, demonstrating how this video app has facilitated new musical practices that intensified participatory culture. Musical presumption is more common on TikTok than on YouTube, and the affordances offered by the video app allow immediate creations that can be easily shared with the community. In this regard, we argue that on YouTube presumption was centered in the production of successful videomemes that become viral and achieve massive audiences, whereas on TikTok presumption depends rather on the success of a practice that is disseminated in the network using hashtags. Besides, TikTok is organized as a global community, not as a personal network of «friends» and «followers», like Facebook, Instagram or Twitter. And last, but not least, TikTok subtracts a step to YouTube in terms of the capability of sharing content due to its idiosyncratic instantaneousness. While on YouTube users first create second upload and finally share the video, tiktokers mainly create and share directly from their phones, although they can also upload videos. Undoubtedly, all this facilitates participation and the viralization of content.

It is easy to anticipate that new musical practices will emerge in the unstable field of online audiovisual platforms and social media. We should be ready to explore them in order to understand how music circulates and is consumed in contemporary society. In this chapter we intended to shed light on the evolution of this panorama by establishing three different periods in the last fifteen years, and we have approached them explaining the practices in their contexts and analysing paradigmatic cases. We are convinced that other periodization and categorization will come up in the next few years, probably paying attention to other issues, and this will help us understand how we produce, circulate, consume and «use» music in the digital era.

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